

AEROELASTIC BEHAVIOR OF A PIEZOELECTRIC ENERGY HARVESTING FLAG UNDER WIND EXCITATION

Dheeraj Tripathi^a, Mehdi Ghommem^a, Abdessattar Abdelkefi^b and Lotfi Romdhane^a

^aDepartment of Mechanical Engineering, American University of Sharjah, Sharjah, United Arab Emirates.

Email: dtripathi@aus.edu

Email: mghommem@aus.edu

Email: lromdhane@aus.edu

^b Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, New Mexico State University, USA.

Email: abdu@nmsu.edu

Abstract. This study aims to advance the understanding of alternative energy sources by exploring flag-based flutter energy harvesters. A smart piezoelectric flag equipped with an MFC patch on a steel substrate is designed and subjected to experimental aeroelastic and energy harvesting analyses under various inflow conditions. The research reveals that under streamlined flow, flutter occurs at higher flow speeds, but can be induced at lower speeds if subcriticality is effectively triggered, thus potentially enhancing energy harvesting at reduced flow speeds. Conversely, under vortex-induced excitation, the flag demonstrates limited energy harvesting potential at smaller gap distances from the upstream bluff body. However, larger gap distances facilitate energy capture at lower flow speeds. The study examines the impact of bluff body diameter on the performance of the piezoelectric flags using cylinder A (2 cm diameter) and cylinder B (3 cm diameter). Results indicate that while cylinder A results in reduced energy harvesting efficiency, cylinder B significantly enhances it. Overall, this study identifies the optimal conditions for maximizing energy harvesting from aeroelastic flutter, considering the combined effects of flag positioning, flow characteristics, bluff body shape, and wind speed. To the best of our knowledge, a hand in hand analysis of these parameters has not been explored in the hitherto literature.

Keywords: Piezoelectric energy harvesting; Subcritical bifurcations; Flutter; MFC; Wind tunnel tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

The growing demand for clean and sustainable energy has led to increased interest in alternative energy solutions [1, 2, 3, 4]. Aeroelastic instabilities, arising from nonlinear fluid-structure interactions, have shown promise as a viable method for energy harvesting [2, 5]. For optimal performance in urban environments, these energy harvesters must capitalize on the in-field aerodynamic conditions to manifest sustained oscillations even at low wind speeds. Therefore, the design of aeroelastic energy harvesters requires a careful balance between lightweight, flexible structures and the durability

necessary to maintain limit cycle oscillations (LCOs) over prolonged periods, ensuring efficient energy harvesting.

Lightweight aeroelastic structures, such as flags [3, 6, 4] or leaf stalks [7, 1, 8], are often used in energy harvester designs. These harvesters are typically examined under either streamlined airflow or vortex-induced flow, the latter occurring when placed downstream of a bluff body that disrupts the airflow. The performance of the harvesters depends upon several factors, including the shape of the flag [1], inflow characteristics, alignment with the flow direction [9], and the distance from the bluff body in vortex-induced inflow conditions [4]. Triangular shapes often exhibit greater instability and power output compared to other shapes [1]. In scenarios involving the vortex-induced inflow, gap distance (G) between the flag and the bluff body is a critical parameter, which not only governs the flag’s aeroelastic behaviour, but also affects the vortex formation mechanism [10]. It is also observed that the shape of the bluff body can have a significant impact on the power output from the harvester [11, 4]. Therefore, efficient energy harvesting from flag flutter in various inflow conditions is a complex multiphysics problem that requires a comprehensive understanding of how multiple parameters interact and influence aeroelastic behaviour as well as the energy harvesting efficiency. This motivates a detailed analysis of energy harvesting performance for a highly flexible piezoelectric flag under varying system parameters. To that end, we propose a smart flag design capable of sustaining oscillations under both streamlined and vortex-induced flows. Aeroelastic and energy harvesting analyses are subsequently conducted on a steel piezoelectric flag equipped with a triangular appendage, subjected to these flow conditions. We investigate various parameters, including bluff body shape, gap distance, and flow speed regimes, to identify effective design conditions for energy harvesting. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the experimental methodology, Section 3 presents the results and discussion, and Section 4 concludes the study.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

The energy harvesting experiments are carried out in the test section (dimensions $0.75\text{ m} \times 0.9\text{ m} \times 1.8\text{ m}$) of a low-speed wind tunnel at the Aeronautics Laboratory, American University of Sharjah. The suction side of the wind tunnel features a honeycomb mesh, ensuring streamlined flow with the turbulence intensity below 1%. A photograph of test section is shown in Fig. 1(a), with data acquisition in Fig. 1(b). The experimental setup includes a triangular steel flag mounted on a metallic platform (Fig. 1(c)). The flag design features a flexible steel beam supporting a triangular flag, with hinges at its free ends. For vortex-induced motion experiments, two different cylindrical bluff bodies with diameters of 2 cm and 3 cm are used upstream of the flag, referred to as cylinder A and cylinder B, respectively, for brevity. Natural frequencies are determined through eigenvalue analysis using *COMSOL Multiphysics*. For the flag beam, the natural frequencies are found to be 3.23 Hz for the first bending mode and 15.96 Hz for the first torsional mode. The properties of different structures used in the experiments are detailed in Table 1.

During the onset of flutter, the triangular flag remains rigid and oscillates about the hinges while the beam undergoes bending deformation. A laser displacement sensor (*Baumer OM70-11112065*) connected to an oscilloscope measures the flag’s bending deflection (y) at the beam’s center (see Fig. 1). Torsional deflections are negligible and not recorded. The energy from the flag flutter is harvested using a MFC patch (*M8528-P2* with d31 effect) with a net active area of $85 \times 28\text{ mm}^2$, attached at the base of the flag beam. The voltage output from this piezoelectric flag, for all the

Figure 1: Experimental setup: (a) photograph of the test section with piezoelectric flag behind bluff body, (b) data acquisition, and (c) schematic of the experimental setup.

Table 1: Specifications of the structures employed in the experiments.

Shape	Dimensions (width or base / height / thickness)
Beam	2 cm / 20 cm / 0.3 mm
Triangular flag	8 cm / 8 cm / 0.3 mm
Cylindrical bluff body A	2 cm (dia.) / 22 cm / 1 mm
Cylindrical bluff body B	3 cm (dia.) / 22 cm / 1 mm

experiments, are obtained across a load resistance of $R = 0.2 \text{ M}\Omega$ and recorded in a PicoScope (see Fig. 1(b)). The average power output from the piezoelectric flag is calculated as $P_{avg} = V_{rms}^2/R$, where V_{rms} is the root mean square voltage. Flow speed (U) is measured using a Vernier anemometer connected to a data acquisition system. All the experiments are performed within the range $U = 0 - 9.0 \text{ m/s}$.

Measurements at two points near the flag, using simultaneous anemometers, show a flow speed difference within $\pm 0.3 \text{ m/s}$ across a range of 0 to 12.0 m/s, indicating high measurement accuracy. To evaluate the uncertainty in aeroelastic response analysis, five flag flutter tests are performed for a gap distance $G = 3d$ behind the 3 cm diameter cylindrical bluff body. The bending, flutter frequency and voltage output responses from these trials are shown in Fig. 2. The mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variance of the test data is listed in Table 2. Overall, the analysis demonstrates the

Table 2: Uncertainty analysis of the test data (Std - Standard deviation, CoV - Coefficient of variance).

Response	Mean	Std	CoV
Voltage	2.44 V	0.11 V	4.34%
Bending amplitude	15.02 mm	1.16 mm	7.69%
Flutter speed	7.7 m/s	0.08 m/s	1.04%
Flutter frequency	3.524 Hz	0.03 Hz	0.83%

Figure 2: Uncertainty quantification of test data: (a) Bending amplitude, (b) Voltage, and (c) Flutter frequency, obtained from five trials

robustness of the data measurement.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Energy harvesting under streamlined flow is analyzed first, by exposing the piezoelectric flag directly to the inflow from the suction side. The experiment is conducted in a forward sweep, increasing the flow speed up to 9.0 m/s, followed by a backward sweep. This method aims to identify any hysteresis in the system response, which indicates subcritical behavior. During the forward sweep (see Fig. 3(a)), flutter onset occurs at approximately $U = 8.7$ m/s, LCOs at a frequency of 3.81 Hz. The average power output from the piezoelectric flag at this speed is $78.41 \mu\text{W}$, remaining nearly constant as the flow speed increases to 9.0 m/s. In the backward sweep (see Fig. 3(b)), LCOs are observed at lower speeds, suggesting potential for energy harvesting at reduced speeds if subcritical conditions are present. The maximum average power output of $86.94 \mu\text{W}$ is recorded at $U = 8.4$ m/s. At $U = 6.2$ m/s, the power output is less than half of the maximum value. LCOs persist down to $U = 5.0$ m/s, but power output is very low below $U = 6.1$ m/s.

Next, the experiments are performed under vortex-induced motion by placing the piezoelectric flag behind either of the cylinders (A or B), at various G values. The flag does not exhibit flutter even at the maximum tested flow speeds ($U = 9.0$ m/s), when very closely placed behind either of the bluff body ($G = 0.5d$). In this case, very small amplitude random oscillations are observed in the flag below 2 mm amplitudes and can not be utilized for the energy harvesting. Even for a higher gap value $G = 3d$, the flag exhibits flutter only under the wake of cylinder B, that too only at $U = 9.0$ m/s. The V_{rms} obtained for this case is 4.16 V, accounting for a $86.32 \mu\text{W}$ power output. At $G = 6d$, flutter is recorded for both the cases. Using cylinder A, the flag undergoes flutter near $U = 8.4$ m/s with a power output of $26.45 \mu\text{W}$. While for cylinder B, the flutter is observed near $U = 7.0$ m/s with a power output of $28.58 \mu\text{W}$ - indicating a similar energy output at almost 20% lesser flow speeds.

Experiments are further continued for increasing the gap between the flag and bluff body. For $G = 9d$, flutter speed is reduced for both the cylinders, enabling the energy harvesting to be possible at lower speeds. For cylinder A, flutter speed is observed near $U = 8.0$ m/s with a $35.11 \mu\text{W}$ power output. For cylinder B, the flutter speed is much lower, close to $U = 6.8$ m/s. The energy output

Figure 3: Responses of piezoelectric flag under streamlined flow (WBB - without bluff body).

is $46.18 \mu W$ - means approximately 31% higher power can be extracted at 18% lower flow speed by replacing the cylinder A with B. For the farthest location of the flag behind the bluff body, *i.e.* $G = 12d$, flutter speed of the flag is reduced close to $U = 7.5$ m/s for cylinder A and $U = 6.2$ m/s for cylinder B. The power output near flutter speed is observed as $25.20 \mu W$ and $10.62 \mu W$, for cylinder A and cylinder B, respectively.

A comparison of the aeroelastic (bending) responses and output voltage responses from the piezoelectric flag for all the test cases at $U = 9.0$ m/s is shown in Fig. 4. The maximum bending deflection (y_{max}) for the case without bluff body (WBB) upstream of flag, *i.e.*, under streamlined inflow conditions, is 23.09 mm with a V_{rms} of 3.97 V (Fig. 4(a)). Under the vortex-induced motion from cylinder A, the y_{max} ranges between 13.86 - 19.61 mm across various gap distances, with the V_{rms} ranging between 3.42 - 3.79 V (Fig. 4(b)-(d)). Hence, for any G value, energy harvesting could not be enhanced using the cylinder A. Nonetheless, the flutter can be achieved at a lower flow velocity, shifting from $U = 8.7$ m/s in the WBB forward sweep case to $U = 7.5$ m/s at $G = 12d$ with cylinder A. The y_{max} and V_{rms} responses are significantly higher when the cylinder A is replaced with the cylinder B (Fig. 4(e)-(h)). In this case, the y_{max} ranges between 18.15 - 24.18 mm and V_{rms} ranges between 3.85 - 5.06 V. Here the maximum V_{rms} of 5.06 V is observed among all test cases at $G = 9d$ corresponding to highest y_{max} (24.18 mm) as well (Fig. 4(g)). Its also worth mentioning that, the flutter speeds are reduced up to $U = 6.2$ m/s (at $G = 12d$) using the cylinder B.

Figure 4: Comparison of aeroelastic responses and voltage output for different experimental configurations at $U = 9.0$ m/s (WBB - without bluff body).

Figure 5 provides a comparative analysis of the power output across different energy harvester configurations, as well as various flow speeds and gap distances. It is evident that the highest power output is achieved with cylinder B within the velocity range of $U = 7.7 - 9.0$ m/s. This is followed by the power output from the backward sweep in the streamlined flow case. However, the energy harvesting potential in the backward sweep scenario remains uncertain, as it is subject to the triggering of subcriticality. In contrast, cylinder A consistently demonstrates a lower power output, particularly at gap distances between $G = 6d$ and $G = 9d$, highlighting its comparatively lower efficiency relative to cylinder B and streamlined flow. A summary of the operational flow speed ranges for various test configurations, along with the corresponding maximum average power extracted from these configurations within their respective operational ranges, is presented in Table 3.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we investigated the effect of different flow conditions, bluff body shapes and relative position of flag and bluff body on the energy harvesting performance of a piezoelectric flag. The salient findings from the study can be summarized as follows:

- Under streamlined flow conditions, the system exhibited subcritical bifurcation behavior. By appropriately triggering this subcriticality, the system has the potential to harvest significant energy at reduced flow speeds regimes.

Figure 5: Power output with different configurations of energy harvesting system (WBB - without bluff body).

Table 3: Operational range and maximum power for different configurations tested.

Configuration	Operational Range		Maximum Average Power	
	Forward	Backward	Forward	Backward
WBB	8.7 - 9.0 m/s	6.1 - 9.0 m/s	78.8 μ W	86.94 μ W
	Cylinder A	Cylinder B	Cylinder A	Cylinder B
$G = 3d$	-	9.0 m/s	-	86.53 μ W
$G = 6d$	8.4 - 9.0 m/s	7.0 - 9.0 m/s	58.48 μ W	75.66 μ W
$G = 9d$	8.0 - 9.0 m/s	6.8 - 9.0 m/s	71.82 μ W	128.02 μ W
$G = 12d$	7.5 - 9.0 m/s	6.2 - 9.0 m/s	59.17 μ W	74.11 μ W

- Energy harvesting using an upstream bluff body to induce vortex motion was found more effective at larger gap values between the piezoelectric flag and the cylinder. Reducing the gap below a certain threshold stabilizes the flag, likely due to feedback effects that alter the wake structure [10].
- Placing cylinder A (2 cm diameter) upstream of the piezoelectric flag reduced the flutter speed compared to the forward sweep under streamlined flow, but resulted in a lower overall power output.
- Cylinder B (3 cm diameter), on the other hand, enhanced the performance of the piezoelectric flag, yielding the highest power output in specific regimes, across all test cases.

Overall, the study presented various configurations aimed at enhancing the energy harvesting from aeroelastic flutter of a piezoelectric flag. The findings highlight the potential for maximizing energy capture, particularly at lower flow speeds. The proposed energy harvesting system can be effectively

integrated in urban settings such as building rooftops, roadside installations, drones, or coastal areas, operating effectively across a range of inflow conditions. Note that, the current analysis is limited to a specific piezoelectric circuit configuration and could be expanded to explore alternative piezoelectric materials and load resistances. Future research could also investigate different bluff body geometries, flag designs, and flow conditions to strategically enhance the energy harvester designs for real-world applications.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the American University of Sharjah under Grants No. PE2404 and No. FRG23-C-E16. We gratefully acknowledge the financial support.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Li, J. Yuan, and H. Lipson. Ambient wind energy harvesting using cross-flow fluttering. *J. Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 109, No. 2, 2011.
- [2] J. McCarthy, S. Watkins, A. Deivasigamani, and S. John. Fluttering energy harvesters in the wind: A review. *J. Sound Vib.*, Vol. 361, pp. 355–377, 2016.
- [3] S. Orrego, K. Shoele, A. Ruas, K. Doran, B. Caggiano, R. Mittal, and S. H. Kang. Harvesting ambient wind energy with an inverted piezoelectric flag. *Appl. Energy*, Vol. 194, pp. 212–222, 2017.
- [4] U. Latif, E. H. Dowell, E. Uddin, M. Younis, and H. Frisch. Comparative analysis of flag-based energy harvester undergoing extraneous induced excitation. *Energy*, Vol. 295, pp. 130995, 2024.
- [5] A. Abdelkefi. Aeroelastic energy harvesting: A review. *Int. J. Eng. Sci.*, Vol. 100, pp. 112–135, 2016.
- [6] M. Eugeni, H. Elahi, F. Fune, L. Lampani, F. Mastroddi, G. P. Romano, and P. Gaudenzi. Numerical and experimental investigation of piezoelectric energy harvester based on flag-flutter. *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.*, Vol. 97, pp. 105634, 2020.
- [7] R. Dickson. New concepts in renewable energy. Lulu Enterprises Inc, pp. 1061, 2008.
- [8] W. Wang, X. He, X. Wang, M. Wang, and K. Xue. A bioinspired structure modification of piezoelectric wind energy harvester based on the prototype of leaf veins. *Sens. Actuators A Phys.*, Vol. 279, pp. 467–473, 2018.
- [9] J. M. McCarthy, et al. An investigation of fluttering piezoelectric energy harvesters in off-axis and turbulent flows. *J. Wind Eng. Ind. Aerodyn.*, Vol. 136, pp. 101–113, 2015.
- [10] Y. Lau, R. So, and R. Leung. Flow-induced vibration of elastic slender structures in a cylinder wake. *J. Fluids Struct.*, Vol. 19, pp. 1061–1083, 2004.
- [11] U. Latif, E. H. Dowell, E. Uddin, and M. Y. Younis. Parametric aerodynamic and aeroelastic study of a deformable flag-based energy harvester for powering low energy devices. *Energy Convers. Manage.*, Vol. 280, p. 116846, 2023.